

NEW METHODS FOR THE SYNTHESIS OF NATURALLY OCCURRING ANTHRAQUINONES*

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Naturally occurring anthraquinone derivatives with one or two possible exceptions are no longer of interest as colouring matters, but their physiological properties appear to justify further study. Hydroxyanthraquinones containing C-methyl, hydroxymethyl, carboxyl and glycosidic groups have long been known to be present in cathartic drugs such as rhubarb, senna, cascara and aloes, from some of which anthrones and anthranols have also been isolated. Stoll¹ showed that the active cathartic constituents of senna, sennoside A and B, are derivatives of 10, 10'-dianthranyl. 2-Methylantraquinone, purpurin, emodin (I), aloë-emodin (II), rhein (III) and barbaloin have been reported to have antibacterial and antitubercular properties.²

Three different lines of investigation led to the suggestion that isonicotinic acid hydrazide killed tubercle bacilli through the intracellular accumulation of hydrogen peroxide,³ but subsequent work⁴ showed that the hypothesis was untenable. Holman⁵ observed that hydrogen peroxide had a curative action on tumours in rats and humans; other workers,^{6, 7, 8, 9} have failed to confirm this, but Sugiura found that a dose of 225 mg./kg. of hydrogen peroxide had a moderate inhibitory effect on sarcoma 180 ascites tumour in rats.⁹ Although from the available evidence it is very improbable that hydrogen peroxide plays any part in antitubercular or antitumour activity, the physiological properties of anthraquinone derivatives are of additional interest because of the observation made by Manchot and Herzog in 1901¹⁰ that hydrogen peroxide is formed when anthrahydroquinone (9,10-dihydroxyanthracene) absorbs oxygen; incidentally, the reduction-oxidation of 2-ethylanthraquinone or 2-*t*-butylanthraquinone is now used for the manufacture of hydrogen peroxide.

At an early stage of our attempts to synthesise a series of naturally occurring anthraquinones and their analogues for an examination of their antitubercular and other physiological properties, it became obvious that the known methods,¹¹ which were usually based on the condensation of nitro- or methoxyphthalic anhydrides with phenols or their ethers, were dependent on relatively inaccessible intermediates and also unsatisfactory from other points of view. Routes starting from common anthraquinonoid dye intermediates were therefore sought, partly because of a wider interest in the reactions of anthraquinone and anthrone derivatives in relation to constitutional problems concerning vat dyes.^{10,12}

Charts I and II illustrate the preparation of emodin (I), physcion (IV), chrysophanol (V), islandicin (VI) and rhein (III) from 1, 5-dinitro- and 1, 8-dinitro-2-methylantraquinone.¹³ After

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the dinitration of 2-methylanthraquinone and separation of the isomers (A. Locher and H. E. Fierz, 1927), a series of reactions are involved, but in general they proceed without difficulty and in good yield.⁹ Experimental conditions for some of the stages have been recently improved; they will be described elsewhere, but a few points may be mentioned. The replacement of chlorine or bromine in α - or β -positions (the latter naturally requiring more vigorous treatment) by methoxy can be effected in over 80% yield; refluxing with sodium methoxide and copper oxide in methanol for 48-72 hours usually gives better yields than heating in a sealed tube at 160-70° for 6-12 hours. Complete demethylation of emodin trimethyl ether to emodin (I) is best effected by heating for a few minutes with aluminium chloride-sodium chloride at 140-50°, and partial demethylation to

CHART I

Emodin and Physcion from 1,8-Dinitro-2-methylanthraquinone.

physcion (IV) by refluxing with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid for an hour. When 1-amino-5-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone (Chart II) is treated with bromine in glacial acetic acid at 20°, the hydroxylated ring is unaffected and the sole product is the 4-bromo compound. The replacement of chlorine or bromine in the α -position by hydroxyl takes place on heating with lime and copper bronze or copper oxide in a sealed tube at 200-10° for 24 hours, but for replacing a β -halogen the temperature has to be raised to 230-50°.

CHART II

Chrysophanol, Islandicin and Rhein from 1, 5-Dinitro-2-methylanthraquinone.

Islandicin (VI) and cynodontin (VII) have been recently synthesised by the persulphate oxidation of the benzoylbenzoic acids (VIII; R = H or OMe), followed by cyclization and

demethylation.¹⁴ As in some of the older methods, this involves the preparation of a mono- or dimethoxyphthalic anhydride.

(VII)

(VIII)

The Marschalk reaction for C-alkylation of amino- and hydroxyanthraquinones by the action of aldehydes in the presence of alkaline hydrosulphite is useful for the synthesis of 2-methylanthraquinone derivatives such as rubiadin (1, 3-dihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone), which Jones and Robertson prepared earlier by two tedious methods involving 2, 6-dichlorotoluene or 2-methoxy-6-nitrotoluene.² Marschalk prepared 1-amino-5-chloro-2-methylanthraquinone from 1-amino-5-chloroanthraquinone, an intermediate for Indanthrene Golden Orange 3C; but in this case the method shown in Chart II is more satisfactory. Other applications of the Marschalk reaction are the synthesis of soranjidiol (1, 6-dihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone) from 1-hydroxy-6-methoxyanthraquinone, which is C-methylated in the 2-position and then demethylated, and the synthesis of morindone (1, 5, 6-trihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone) from 1, 2, 5-trihydroxyanthraquinone (Brilliant Alizarin Bordeaux R) by direct C-methylation in the 6-position or through the 2-methyl ether. Alizarin does not undergo the Marschalk reaction under the usual conditions. Morindone brominates in the 7-position, and the further action of lime under pressure should lead to copareolatin (1, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone), isolated by Briggs² from *Coprosma areolata*, a New Zealand plant.¹⁵

Xanthopurpurin and purpurin readily undergo a Mannich base reaction with formaldehyde and dialkylamines at room temperature, yielding (IX) and (X).¹⁶ Such basic derivatives of anthraquinone may have interest from several points of view because of their physical and chemical properties. Dimethylaminomethylxanthopurpurin (IX: R = Me) was kindly tested by Dr. V. C. Barry, who reported in January 1958 that it partially inhibited *M. tuberculosis* (H37Rv; Proskauer and Beck medium containing 5% human serum) at a dilution of 100,000; the anthraquinone ring in this case has probably little significance, since a similar Mannich base from orcinol- γ -carboxylic acid exhibited activity of the same order. Purpurin condenses smoothly with formaldehyde and diethanolamine to form (X; R = CH₂CH₂OH), from which (XI) can be prepared; (XI) may be of some interest in cancer studies as a biological alkylating agent and as a quinone with metal-chelating properties. The only reference in the literature to a Mannich base condensation in the anthraquinone series, other than the cited patent,¹⁶ is the preparation of the Mannich bases from formaldehyde, iminodiacetic acid and alizarin, 1,2,5-, 1,2,6- and 1,2,7-trihydroxyanthraquinones, and quinalizarin;¹⁷ "very little nitrogenous product was obtained from the corresponding reaction with 2-hydroxy-, 1, 4-, 1,5-, or 1, 8-dihydroxy-, or 1, 2, 3- or 1, 2, 4-trihydroxyanthraquinone." The reaction was carried out at 75°, using excess of the aldehyde and acid (as the disodium salt), and the products (obtained as yellow or orange-brown powders in 13% yield from alizarin and unspecified yield in the other cases) were examined as complexometric indicators in EDTA titrations.¹⁷ It is doubtful if the products described by Belcher, Leonard and West¹⁷ had the structures ascribed to them. On the other hand purpurin, which they found to be

unreactive, reacts readily with formaldehyde and iminodiacetic acid at room temperature, yielding (X; R = CH₂COOH) as red needles.¹⁴

Derivatives of 2-Anthraquinonylcarbinol and Anthraquinone-2-aldehydes

Mitter and Banerjee in 1932 converted rhein diacetate into aloë-emodin (II) in unspecified yield via the acid chloride and aldehyde, and until a few years ago this was the only synthesis of a natural anthraquinonylcarbinol. Brown and Subba Rao have described the reduction of carboxylic acids to the corresponding primary alcohols by sodium borohydride-aluminium chloride in diglyme or by diborane in any other medium.¹⁸ Preliminary experiments showed that the former procedure was not suitable for the reduction of anthraquinone carboxylic acids containing hydroxyl or acetoxy groups; but rhein diacetate in diglyme (diethylene glycol dimethyl ether) or monoglyme (ethylene glycol dimethyl ether) underwent smooth reduction to the carbinol by passing diborane (generated by adding a diglyme solution of sodium borohydride to boron trifluoride-etherate in diglyme) at room temperature until an intense orange to red colour developed. Hydrolysis of the product with cold dilute sodium hydroxide solution gave aloë-emodin (II) in an overall yield of about 60%. Citreorsein (XII; ω-hydroxyemodin), a metabolite of *Penicillium citreo-rösum* and *P. cyclopium*,¹¹ was similarly prepared from emodic acid triacetate (XIII).¹⁹ Natural citreorsein for comparison was kindly supplied by Professor T. Posternak.

An important feature of the action of diborane on anthraquinone-2-carboxylic acids was the preferential reduction of the carboxyl group, the quinone group being attacked only at a later stage. In this connection it seemed desirable to examine the action of a mixture of sodium borohydride

and boron trifluoride-etherate, as distinct from diborane, on anthraquinone derivatives, and a new general method for their reduction to anthracene derivatives thus became available. When a suspension of anthraquinone in diglyme was treated successively with sodium borohydride and boron trifluoride-etherate, both in diglyme, at 25-30° with agitation for two hours, anthracene was obtained in about 70% yield.²⁰ By varying the conditions slightly the following reductions could be carried out: 1-chloroanthraquinone → 1-chloroanthracene; 2-chloroanthraquinone → 2-chloroanthracene; 2-aminoanthraquinone → 2-aminoanthracene; 2-hydroxyanthraquinone → 2-hydroxyanthracene; 2-methoxyanthraquinone → 2-methoxyanthracene; anthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid → anthracene-2-carbinol; 3, 4, 9, 10-dibenzopyrene-5, 8-quinone → 3, 4, 9, 10-dibenzopyrene;²¹ 2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone → 2-methylnaphthalene. This new procedure for the reduction of anthraquinones to anthracene derivatives promises to be useful for investigating the constitution of naturally occurring quinones as well as anthraquinonoid vat dyes.

Teloschistin, isolated by Seshadri²² from the Indian lichen *Teloschistes flavicans*, and fallacinal, isolated by Murakami²³ from the Japanese lichen *Xanthoria fallax*, have been assigned the same structure (XIV), the 7-monomethyl ether of ω -hydroxyemodin (citreorosein); but different melting points were quoted for teloschistin (245-47°) and fallacinal (236-37°). By the partial methylation of ω -hydroxyemodin, a monomethyl ether, m.p. 229-31°, was obtained;²⁴ the first reports on teloschistin stated that it melted at 229-30°, and that the m.p. was undepressed by mixing with the 7-monomethyl ether of ω -hydroxyemodin. Both Seshadri and Murakami described the synthesis of (XIV), possessing the same m.p. as natural teloschistin and fallacinal respectively, by the treatment of 4, 5-diacetoxy-7-methoxy-2-bromomethylantraquinone (XV) with silver acetate or sodium acetate.

Murakami found that fallacinal was accompanied by the corresponding aldehyde, fallacinal, which was subsequently isolated also from *Teloschistes flavicans*.²²

In the synthesis of teloschistin²², physcion (parietin) diacetate was brominated with *N*₂bromosuccinimide (NBS), following the earlier procedure for the conversion of rubiadin to lucidin in which two molecules of the brominating agent were used;² (XV) was obtained as a "sticky solid," which was not purified or analysed and was used directly for conversion into teloschistin triacetate. It appears probable that the compound, believed to be (XV), consisted largely of the dibromomethyl derivative, and the ultimate product was the aldehyde, fallacinal, rather than the alcohol (XIV). Murakami²³ used only one molecule of NBS for the bromination of physcion diacetate; he too did not isolate the bromo compound (XV) in the pure state, but treated the crude product with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide, and chromatographed a benzene solution of the product on calcium hydrogen phosphate, pretreated with phosphoric acid. Eight bands separated, and fallacinal was recovered from the top band.

The tetra-acetate of natural catenarin (XVI) has been converted by Neelakantan, Pocker and Raistrick to trisporin (XVII) by the ω -bromination method; the action of NBS on catenarin tetra-acetate yielded a "rather complex mixture of reaction products" from which "a crude

bromoacetate" was isolated; treatment of this bromoacetate with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave tritispurin penta-acetate.²⁶

(XVI)

(XVII)

In the NBS method of bromination of 2-methylanthraquinones, not containing acetoxy groups in both the adjacent positions as in rubiadin diacetate which readily yielded 1, 3-diacetoxy-2-bromomethylanthraquinone,² the molar proportion of the brominating agent is important. Ayyangar and Joshi found that, when two molecules of NBS were used for one of 1-acetoxy-3-methylanthraquinone, the product was 1-acetoxy-3-dibromomethylanthraquinone, which was hydrolysed to 1-hydroxyanthraquinone-3-aldehyde by cold sulphuric acid; but when exactly one molecule of NBS was used, the pure monobromo compound was isolable, and treatment with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave 1-acetoxy-3-acetoxymethylanthraquinone in good yield. Aloe-emodin was similarly prepared from chrysophanol diacetate.²⁶

By the action of formaldehyde in sodium hydroxide solution, xanthopurpurin readily undergoes hydroxymethylation in the 2-position, yielding lucidin (XVIII); lucidin can be oxidised to the aldehyde (XIX) by manganese dioxide in boiling benzene, and to munjistin (the corresponding carboxylic acid) by alkaline silver oxide.² The aldehyde (XIX) is of interest because it was subsequently isolated from the heartwood of *Morinda tinctoria*,²⁷ the 1-monomethyl ether (damnacanthol) accompanies lucidin 1-monomethyl ether (damnacanthol) in the root of *Damnacanthus major*.²⁸

Damnacanthol has been synthesised from lucidin via the 2, 3-diacetate and its 1-methyl ether prepared by the action of diazomethane in tetrachloroethane; damnacanthol was then oxidized to damnacanthol by manganese dioxide.^{29,30}

(XVIII)

(XIX)

Unlike xanthopurpurin, purpurin gave the corresponding hexahydroxydianthraquinonyl-methane, and not the 3-hydroxymethyl derivative (XX), by treatment with formaldehyde and sodium hydroxide solution. The action of formaldehyde and conc. sulphuric acid on purpurin also failed to yield (XX), contrary to Hill and Richter; the product had the properties (analysis, infrared spectrum, alkali -insolubility, formation of diacetate and dimethyl ether) of the 1, 3-dioxan (XXI).³ 3-Hydroxymethylpurpurin (XX) has now been prepared from 3-methylpurpurin by the ω -bromination method.²⁸

The facile hydroxymethylation of xanthopurpurin to lucidin is useful for the synthesis of analogous anthraquinonylcarbinols and for characterizing 1, 3-dihydroxyanthraquinones, unsubstituted in the 2-position. Hydroxymethylation of 1, 3, 8-trihydroxyanthraquinone gave the 2-hydroxymethyl derivative (XXII),²⁹ which proved to be different from versicolorin, a colouring matter isolated by Hatsuda and Kuyama³¹ from the mycelium of *Aspergillus versicolor*, for which they suggested the alternative structures (XXII) or (XXIII). However, (XXII) has been found to be identical with coelulatin, a pigment isolated from *Coelospermum reticulatum* by R. G. Cooke.³² In a private communication Dr. Cooke has stated that a point of interest in the constitution of coelulatin is that it occurs in a plant belonging to the family Rubiaceae and "the rule against the occurrence of 1, 8-dihydroxyanthraquinones in this family will now have to be stated in a different form." The isomer (XXIII) has more recently been synthesised by the ω -bromination of 1, 3, 8-triacetoxy-7-methylanthraquinone, replacement of bromine by acetoxy, and hydrolysis; (XXIII) also did not agree in some of its properties with versicolorin, and the constitution of this pigment therefore needs further investigation.²⁶

The tentative structure (XXIV) was assigned by Tschirch and Lüdy to erythrolaccin, a yellow pigment isolated from stick-lac.¹¹ Erythrolaccin has now been shown to be constituted as (XXV),³³ one of the steps in the argument being that it has a xanthopurpurin nucleus unsubstituted in the 2-position because it can be hydroxymethylated by formaldehyde and sodium hydroxide solution; colour reactions, dyeing properties and infrared spectra placed the other two hydroxyls in 1, 2-positions. A choice between (XXV) and (XXVI) was made in favour of (XXV), because of the evidence obtained by Briggs for the structure of alaternin (XXVI), a constituent of the bark of *Rhamnus alaternus*.

(XXVI)

Attempts are in progress to synthesise rhodocladonic acid by an application of the hydroxy-methylation and oxidation methods which led to lucidin and munjistin from xanthopurpurin.

CHART III

*Biogenesis of Endocrocin, Emodin and Hypericin.*³⁴

Anthraquinone carboxylic acids are of special interest as likely intermediates in the biogenesis of emodin and other hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinones. Endocrocin (XXVII) in particular occupies a key position, since it can be derived from eight molecules of acetic acid through the heptaketopalmitic acid (XXVIII) as suggested by Robinson,³⁴ who has also drawn attention to the possibility of the anthrone (XXIX) being a precursor of hypericin (XXX), the photodynamic constituent of *Hypericum perforatum* (Chart III).³⁵

Endocrocin (XXVII) is accompanied by physcion (IV) in the lichen *Nephromopsis endocrocea*,³⁶ and by catenarin (XVI) as a metabolite of *Aspergillus amstelodami*.³⁷ It has been very recently found to be a product of the ergot fungus (*Claviceps purpurea*),³⁸ and of an ultraviolet mutant of *Penicillium islandicum* from which emodin (I), catenarin (XVI) and islandicin (VI) were isolated earlier.³⁹

Although the structure of endocrocin (XXVII) is based on adequate evidence, its confirmation by synthesis seemed desirable. In order to devise a suitable method for introducing the carboxyl group in the desired position, the synthesis of the unknown 1-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid (XXXI) was first undertaken. The route ultimately followed is shown in Chart IV.⁴⁰ The direct conversion of 1-nitro-2,3-dimethylanthraquinone to the amino-acid (XXXII) by alkali treatment was not feasible.⁴¹ The isoxazole (XXXIII) was prepared by a known method⁴² with the object of carrying out a reductive hydrolysis to 1-amino-3-methylanthraquinone-2-aldehyde, following German patents, and then oxidation to the acid (XXXII), but the yields were very poor. The isoxazole was then found to be hydrolysable to the acid (XXXII) in 50-60% yield by heating with 40% alcoholic potassium hydroxide.

CHART IV

Synthesis of 1-Hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid.

The dinitration of 2,3-dimethylanthraquinone gave an easily separable mixture of the 1,5- and 1,8-dinitro derivatives. An interesting by-product in the nitration, obtained in high yield

by employing suitable conditions, was 1, 4, 5-trinitro-2, 3-dimethylantraquinone. Starting from 1, 5-dinitro-2, 3-dimethylantraquinone a synthesis of endocrocin by the reactions outlined in Chart V is in progress.⁴⁰

CHART V
A Route to Endocrocin.

The partial reduction of 1, 5-dinitro-2, 3-dimethylantraquinone to 1-nitro-5-amino-2, 3-dimethylantraquinone was effected by the known method of heating with dimethylaniline, and the position of the amino group was confirmed by deamination to 1-nitro-2, 3-dimethylantraquinone. For the conversion of the nitro compound (XXXIV) to the isoxazole (XXXV) 20% oleum at 25° proved more satisfactory than aluminium chloride at 160°. The hydrolysis of the isoxazole (XXXV) to the amino-acid (XXXVI) presented considerable difficulty. On treatment with 40% alcoholic potash at the reflux for 4 hours, the isoxazole (XXXV) gave (XXXVI) in poor yield.

accompanied by a monobromo compound. Lime under pressure on the corresponding α -hydroxy compound gave a product which, on complete methylation by the potassium carbonate-dimethyl sulphate method, gave an ether-ester melting at 210° , but it did not depress the m.p. of the ether-ester from natural endocrocin, $225-26^\circ$, kindly supplied by Professor Shibata. Hydrolysis of (XXXV) with boiling methanolic baryta was found to give a better yield of (XXXVI), but this was again accompanied by the 6-bromo compound. When the mixture was submitted to the usual reactions for replacement of the amino group and the bromine atoms by hydroxyl, the main product appeared to be 1, 6-dihydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid, since the ultraviolet and visible absorption spectrum resembled that of 1, 6-dihydroxyanthraquinone, rather than endocrocin and emodin, although it exhibited the colour reactions of endocrocin. Improved conditions for the hydrolysis of the isoxazole (XXXV) are being studied, as well as alternative routes involving preferential attack on the 2-methyl group in 1, 5-dinitro-2, 3-dimethylanthraquinone.

(XXXVII)

(XXXVIII)

Another route to endocrocin which was examined was through the isoxazole (XXXVII) obtained in about 20% yield by treatment of 1, 5-dinitro-2, 3-dimethylanthraquinone with oleum; but hydrolysis of the isoxazole with alcoholic potash gave a compound analysing for 1-amino-5-hydroxy-3-methylanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid (XXXVIII) and not 1-amino-5-nitro-3-methylanthraquinone-2-carboxylic acid. The action of methanolic baryta on (XXXVII) also did not yield the desired product*.

* The infrared spectrum of endocrocin has a band at 1720 cm.^{-1} which is too high for an aromatic carboxylic acid. The possibility that endocrocin is emodin- ω -carboxylic acid has to be considered, and this is now being synthesized.

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